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Fon Morphosyntactic Issues in Translation

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Overview of the Presentation

Translation as a social process extends our relationship with various cultures, languages, communities, others, and even ourselves (Venuti, 2021, p. 2–3). This sociological interaction often influences the mediator’s psychological, cultural, and linguistic perspectives in translation. In addition, many theoretical idiosyncrasies of translation studies in scholarly discourse over the years have considered and still consider the sociological attribute of translation as a reflective and interpretative art that cannot be realized in isolation from the existing social factors (Latour, 2016, p. 30; Passiani & Reuillard, 2023, p. 3).

However, if the fundamental struggle of translation practice is to achieve maximum linguistic and cultural equivalence, as stated by Schleiermacher (2021, p. 60–62), then the translator’s task remains increasingly complicated. As such, translations involving African languages usually face special sociolinguistic conditions due to the complex structure and the cultural elements deeply rooted in such languages, especially under-resourced languages. That is the case with

Fon, the major language spoken in the Benin Republic, whose tonal and morphosyntactic structures pose problems in translation and could result in aggravated pitfalls when juxtaposed against European languages, especially French and English.

In this exploratory study, I aim to provide an overview of Fon language as well as the status of French and English as foreign languages in Benin Republic, and explore the challenges faced by the translator in translating morphosyntactic elements of Fon into French and English, with a view to suggesting strategies for a successful mediation of tonal and morphosyntactic divides for mutual, intercultural understanding and diplomacy between the African and Western languages.

I will employ Robert Lado's Contrastive Analysis Theory (1957) throughout this study as an approach concerned with the evaluation of differences and similarities between languages—the interaction between the source text and the target text (Shang, 2023, p. 189). Here, the source language remains Fon, while both French and English are the target languages. The differences and similarities are determined based on a

"common point for departure" (James, 1980, p. 42). In this case, the common ground or point is the morphosyntax of the Fon language vis-à-vis that of French and English.

I will also use the methodology of Contrastive Analysis established by distinctive scholars of the field (Shang, 2023, p. 189): "any Contrastive Analysis involves two steps: first, there is the stage of *description* when each of the two languages is described on the appropriate level; the second stage is the stage of *juxtaposition for comparison*" (James, 1980, p. 30). Scholars also improve on the Contrastive Analysis Theory and interpret the two steps above to be three: "A classical contrastive analysis consists of three steps, not always clearly distinguishable in the analysis itself but always tacitly assumed: (1) *description*; (2) *juxtaposition*; (3) *comparison*" (Krzeszowsky, 1990, p. 35). The argument remains that the steps do not appear in isolation during analysis and that they are implicitly included in James' two steps, as mentioned above. The three-step methodology is fit for the analysis of the current study.